

Arsonophenyl and Sulphonamidophenyl Derivatives of N-Aryl Rhodanines

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5-Arsonophenyl and 5-sulphonamidophenyl derivatives of eight N-aryl rhodanines have been synthesised for possible use as amoebicides and bactericides.

Organo-arsenicals, sulphanilamides and rhodanine derivatives are quite well known for their therapeutic properties. In continuation of our work^{1,2}, it was considered of interest to prepare some 5-arsonophenyl N-aryl rhodanines and 5-sulphonamidophenyl N-aryl rhodanines as potential amoebicides and bactericides respectively.

N-aryl rhodanines were prepared by the method of Rout *et al.*³ Diazotized arsanilic acid and sulphanilamide were coupled with 3-N-aryl rhodanines and the resulting compounds were decomposed with splitting off of nitrogen¹⁻².

Previously it has been shown that arsonophenyl, or sulphonamidophenyl, group is attached to an active methylene group, which is in alpha-position to an activating carbonyl group. The active nature of methylene group in the 5-position of rhodanine has been well established⁴⁻⁵. In light of the above evidence it has been assumed that the arsonophenyl and sulphonamidophenyl groups are attached to the 5-position of N-aryl rhodanines.

EXPERIMENTAL

5-Arsonophenyl N-phenyl rhodanine : *p*-Arsanilic acid (1.8 g.) was diazotised and the resulting solution was added slowly with stirring to a solution of N-phenyl rhodanine (2 g.) in acetone alcohol mixture (50 ml.) containing sodium acetate (4.5 g.) at 0-5°. This was followed by dropwise addition of a solution of cupric chloride (3 g.) in water (10 ml.) with stirring during 3 to 4 hrs at 0°. The reaction mixture was warmed on the water-bath (40-50°) for 4-5 hrs till the evolution of gas ceased. The buff coloured copper salt was collected, decomposed with 2*N* sodium hydroxide solution. Cupric hydroxide was removed by filtration and the filtrate was acidified carefully with dilute acetic acid. The substance which separated out on standing was collected and dried, (m.p. > 300°, yield 55%). (Found : C, 43.91; H, 2.85; S, 15.32; N, 3.18; As, 18.13%. C₁₅H₁₂S₂NO₄As requires : C, 44.01; H, 2.93; S, 15.64; N, 3.42; As, 18.33%).

Other arsonophenyl derivatives were prepared similarly and their analytical data and m.p. are given in Table I.

1. H. K. Pujari and M. K. Rout, *J. Sci. and Ind. Research*, 1955, **14B**, 563.
2. A. K. Panigrahi, P. K. Jesthi and M. K. Rout, *J. and Proc. Inst. Chem.*, 1966, **38**, 175.
3. B. Sahoo, P. B. Tripathy and M. K. Rout, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 421.
4. B. Das, B. K. Patnaik and M. K. Rout, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 603.
5. F. C. Brown, *Chem. Revs*, 1961, **61**, 463.

TABLE I

5-Arsonophenyl *N*-aryl rhodanines :

No.	Nature of aryl group 'R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Arsenic		% Nitrogen	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	> 300	55	18.13	18.33	3.18	3.42
2.	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	> 300	65	16.79	16.9	3.11	3.15
3.	<i>m</i> -Chloro phenyl	> 300	60	16.83	16.9	3.99	3.15
4.	<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	> 300	60	16.74	16.9	3.07	3.15
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	> 300	50	17.46	17.73	3.21	3.31
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	> 300	55	17.58	17.73	3.19	3.31
7.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	> 300	50	17.64	17.73	3.24	3.31
8.	<i>p</i> -Ethyl phenyl	> 300	45	16.41	16.55	2.96	3.09

5-Sulphonamidophenyl *N*-phenyl rhodanine : Sulphanilamide (1 g.) was diazotised and the resulting solution was added slowly with stirring to a solution of *N*-phenyl rhodanine (1 g.) in acetone alcohol mixture (50 ml.) containing sodium acetate (3 g.) at 0–5°. A solution of cupric chloride (2 g.) in water (10 ml.) was then added dropwise during 3 to 4 hrs at 0°. The reaction mixture was warmed on the water bath (40–50°) with stirring for 4–5 hrs till the evolution of gas ceased. The product which separated out was washed with hot water and finally crystallised from ethanol. (M.P. > 300°, Yield—65%) (Found : C, 49.14; H, 3.09; S, 26.17; N, 7.59%; $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{S}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$ requires C, 49.34; H, 3.29; S, 26.39; N, 7.69%).

The analytical data, m.p. of sulphonamidophenyl derivatives of other *N*-aryl rhodanines are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

5-Sulphonamidophenyl *N*-aryl rhodanines :

No.	Nature of aryl group R	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Nitrogen		% Sulphur	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	> 300	65	7.59	7.69	26.17	26.37
2.	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	> 300	60	6.96	7.03	23.95	24.10
3.	<i>m</i> -Chloro phenyl	> 300	65	6.95	7.03	24.12	24.10
4.	<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	> 300	55	6.99	7.03	23.93	24.10
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	> 300	60	7.38	7.40	25.32	25.40
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	> 300	63	7.36	7.40	25.35	25.40
7.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	> 300	55	7.33	7.40	25.29	25.40
8.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxy phenyl	298(d)*	50	6.77	6.86	23.47	23.53

(d)* denotes decomposition.

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